

to inhibit the fungal growth completely even at 2000 ppm and is the most effective of the series.

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Synthesis of New Quinoline Derivatives as Antiamoebic Agents

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A large number of quinoline derivatives especially where the methyl or a methoxy substituent is at the '8' position are effective against microbial

diseases. Misra and Saxena¹⁻³ have reported some quinolines having a good activity against *E. histolytica* at a conc. of 125 µg/ml. Also, a group of anils have shown good activity against *E. coli*⁴⁻⁸. Recently, Misra and Agarwal⁹ have synthesised some substituted sulphazino quinolines and their anils which have shown considerable antiamoebic activity. The thiadiazoles, especially the thiadiazolyl urea¹⁰ and the 2-amino-1, 3, 4-thiadiazole¹¹, have been reported to exhibit remarkable insecticidal properties.

These observations prompted us to synthesize some 2-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl-5-thio, 2-methyl-6' or 7' or 8' aryl substituted quinolines and 2-arylamino-1, 3, 4-thiadiazolyl-5-thio-4'-carboxymethyl, 2-methyl-6' or 7' or 8' aryl substituted quinolines.

The compounds were single substances (tlc, benzenemethanol, 10 : 1). The thiadiazoles so prepared were characterised by their analytical and spectral data. Their ir (KBr) showed the presence of bands as follows : NH (3200), cyclic N=C=S (1470), cyclic N-N=C (1240), -S (1340) and C-Cl (820).

Experimental

4-Aryl thiosemicarbazides, 2-arylamino-5-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazoles, 2-methyl-6 or 7 or 8 aryl substituted 4-hydroxy quinolines and 2-methyl-6 or 7 or 8 aryl substituted 4-chloroquinolines were prepared as described in literature¹²⁻¹⁶.

2-Arylamino-1, 3, 4-thiadiazolyl-5-thio, 2-methyl-6' or 7' or 8' aryl substituted quinolines. I.: Sodium salts of 2-arylamino-5-mercapto-1, 3, 4-thiadiazole were prepared according to Sen Gupta *et al*¹⁷. The sodium salts were treated with substituted chloroquinolines (0.01 mole) in Na₂CO₃ solution (1.75 g in 10 ml water) and finally dimethyl formamide (10 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 hrs. It was cooled, diluted with water and filtered. The filtrate was acidified with conc. HCl and the precipitate so obtained washed with water, dried and recrystallised from dilute methanol.

The quinoline derivatives thus prepared (45-50% yield) are described in Table 1.

2'-Methyl-6' or 7' or 8' aryl substituted-4'-carboxychloromethyl quinolines. II.: The substituted hydroxyquinoline (0.01 mole) was treated with chloroacetyl chloride (0.01 mole) in dry benzene and the mixture refluxed for 2-3 hrs. The contents were cooled, filtered and washed with ice-cold water. The compound (40-50% yield) was dried and recrystallised from ethanol.

Two such compounds were synthesised : a. 2'-methyl-4'-carboxychloromethyl quinoline, m.p. 215°, b. 2', 8'-dimethyl-4'-carboxychloromethyl quinoline, m.p. 217-218°.

TABLE 1

Aryl Group	R	m.p. °C
1. phenyl	H	170
2. <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	H	166
3. <i>p</i> -tolyl	H	208
4. <i>p</i> -anisyl	H	198
5. phenyl	<i>o</i> -tolyl	170
6. <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	<i>o</i> -tolyl	211
7. <i>p</i> -tolyl	<i>o</i> -tolyl	190
8. <i>p</i> -anisyl	<i>o</i> -tolyl	178

All melting points are uncorrected. Nitrogen analysis of all compounds was found to be satisfactory.

2-Arylamino-1, 3, 4-thiadiazolyl-5-thio-4'-carboxymethyl-2'-methyl-6' or 7' or 8' aryl substituted quinolines: The sodium salts of 2-arylamino-1, 3, 4-thiadiazole were treated with II (0.01 mole) in Na_2CO_3 solution (1.75 g in 10 ml water) and finally dimethyl formamide (10 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 hrs and cooled. It was then diluted with water and filtered. The filtrate was acidified with conc. HCl. The precipitate so obtained was washed well with water, dried and recrystallised from dilute methanol (Table 2). Compounds were obtained in 50-65% yields.

TABLE 2

Aryl group	R	m.p. °C
1. phenyl	H	198
2. <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	H	162
3. <i>p</i> -tolyl	H	178
4. <i>p</i> -anisyl	H	180
5. phenyl	<i>o</i> -tolyl	196
6. <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	<i>o</i> -tolyl	194
7. <i>p</i> -tolyl	<i>o</i> -tolyl	212
8. <i>p</i> -anisyl	<i>o</i> -tolyl	220(d)

All melting points are uncorrected. Nitrogen analysis of all the compounds was found to be satisfactory.

Biological screening: Of the sixteen compounds synthesised, fifteen were tested against the axenic culture of *E. histolytica* at a concentration of 62.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. None of the compounds was found to possess any significant amoebicidal activity.

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Anti-Inflammatory and Anti-Proteolytic Activity of Some Newly Synthesized Phenothiazine Derivatives

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PHENOTHIAZINE derivatives exhibit a variety of biological activities and are used clinically as tranquillizer¹ and anti-histaminics². Anti-inflammatory activity has been reported in metiazinic acid³ (10-methyl phenothiazine-2-acetic acid) and several substituted piperidine-phenothiazines⁴. Moreover, the anti-inflammatory activity of piperazines and piperidines is well documented^{5,6}.

Fourteen new substituted phenothiazines linked with piperazines and morpholines were synthesized and evaluated for their anti-inflammatory activity. Since proteolytic enzymes⁷ have been shown to play an important role in the process of inflammation, the compounds were also studied for their anti-proteolytic activity.

* Part of the work will be incorporated in Ph.D. thesis of M. Verma.

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